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Research Article

**ELECTROSPUN QUERCETIN LOADED NANOFIBER USING
PVA AND PEG POLYMER FOR MANAGEMENT OF
HYPERTENSION.**¹Jadhavar Nilesh Govind, ²Dr. Bhushure O.G., ³Dr. Mani Ganesh, ⁴Lanjile Indrajit,
⁵Dr. Hyun Tae Jang, ⁶Akash S. Jaybhaye¹ Channabasweshwar College (Degree) Latur - 413512 , Maharashtra, India² Channabasweshwar College (Degree) Latur - 413512 , Maharashtra, India³ Channabasweshwar College (Degree) Latur - 413512 , Maharashtra, India⁴ Channabasweshwar College (Degree) Latur - 413512 , Maharashtra, India⁵ Department of Chemical Engineering Hanseo University, Hanseo-2gil, Haemi-myun, Seosan-si, South Korea⁶ Raosaheb Patil Danve College of Pharmacy, Badnapur**Abstract:**

Purpose: The purpose of this study was to formulate and evaluate QUERCETIN loaded nanofiber to improve bioavailability of quercetin for enhanced solubility. Among the various polymers PVA and PEG was used.

Methods: Nanofibers were prepared by electrospinning method. First, the polymers were selected, and then a suitable solvent was chosen based on the polymer's solubility. Then respective solvent was used for electrospinning. Different batches of nanofibers were produced based on various ratios. Electrospinning was then performed to obtain these different nanofiber batches. The formulation was optimized using criteria such as lightweight properties, small diameters, controllable pore structures, and a high surface-to-volume ratio. The optimized formulation batch (N-2) was taken and subjected to various thermodynamic studies. It was then evaluated for different characteristics, including FTIR, DSC, XRD, entrapment efficiency, and SEM studies.

Results-Based on the 94 % drug release rate and the good solubility of the nanofiber in PBS Ph 4.5 it was determined that the solubility of the nanofiber is 1.5 times higher than that of pure Quercetin. Nanofibers exhibit a large surface area, porosity, and adaptable surface functions, which could aid in reducing symptoms of hypertension associated with Quercetin by enhancing drug delivery and bioavailability.

Keywords –Electrospinning, Nanofiber, Hypertension, Quercetin.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension

Hypertension, typically defined as sustained blood pressure in medical settings of 140/90 mm Hg or higher, is a significant contributor to premature morbidity and mortality in the United States. By 2025, global hypertension prevalence is projected to rise by 60%, affecting 1.56 billion people. Developing nations will see an 80% increase, highlighting a growing health challenge worldwide. High blood pressure is a leading precursor to both systolic and diastolic heart failure, a primary cause of hospitalizations among Medicare recipients.

Quercetin, a flavonoid found in many plants, is widely available over-the-counter and often taken as a dietary supplement. It is reputed for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, and potential anticarcinogenic properties. Quercetin combats oxidative stress by scavenging free radicals, thus reducing tissue damage and inflammation. It also inhibits the release of inflammatory substances and an enzyme involved in glucose breakdown.

Material science and nanotechnology are rapidly advancing fields offering significant improvements in material properties. Research in these areas enhances comfort and functionality across various applications. Nanofibers can be produced through methods like drawing, template synthesis, and electrospinning. Electrospinning, utilizing electrical forces, produces polymer nanofibers with exceptionally fine structural characteristics, offering unique advantages in diverse applications.

The first electrospinning experiments utilized cellulose acetate in acetone and monomethyl ether of glycol solvents under 57 kV, leading to the first patent in this pioneering field.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials

The material used in nanofiber formulation of Quercetin are obtained from different source such as PVA(Poly Vinyl Alcohol) (Labware Chemicals pvt ltd.) PEG (Poly Ethylene Glycol)(Himedia Laboratories Pvt Ltd.) Quercetin (Labware Chemicals pvt ltd.) DI-Methylformaamide (Cosmo Chem Pune LaboratoryChemicals) etc.

Methodology

PREFORMULAION STUDIE

Standard calibration curve

100mg drug (quercetin) was dissolved in 100ml DMF(dimethyl formaamide) solvent. 1000µg/ml concentration solution was prepared. 10ml solution pipette out and added into 100ml of DMF and 100µg/ml solution was prepared. Serial dilution in concentration range 5-25 µg/ml were prepared from

standard solution. The UV absorbance of these solution was determined spectrophotometrically at 376nm using double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Infrared Spectrum

Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were obtained on a Perkin Elmer spectrometer at room temperature following after the formation of a nanofiber. 09 scans were taken at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution over the range of 4000-400 cm.

Drug-polymers compatibility studies

Drug polymers interaction holds great importance in new formulation development. Before drug formulation it is essential to evaluate the possible interactions between the active principle and the polymers used for the formulation, as the choice of the polymers should be performed in relation to the drug delivery, to their compatibility with the same drug and to the stability of the final product. In this regard FTIR and DSC are more suitable tool. In this study we used FTIR spectral study for compatibility studies. For this FTIR for pure drug, individual polymer and physical mixture of drug and polymer were subjected to FTIR analysis to observe if any compatibility issues among them.

Scanning Electron Microscopy:

When characterizing quercetin using SEM, researchers might be interested in observing its physical characteristics such as particle size, shape, and surface features. By examining quercetin particles under SEM, scientists can gain insights into its morphology, which can be crucial for various applications including drug delivery, food technology, and nanotechnology. SEM allows for detailed imaging of quercetin particles at nanometer-scale resolution, providing valuable information about their structural properties.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry:

In quercetin characterization, DSC helps researchers understand its thermal properties, including its melting behavior, crystallinity, and thermal stability. Here's how DSC works and its role in quercetin characterization: DSC measures the heat flow (either absorbed or released) in a sample as a function of temperature or time. It compares the heat flow to a reference material under controlled heating conditions. As the temperature of the sample is gradually increased, any heat absorbed or released by the sample is recorded by the DSC instrument. This can include endothermic (heat absorbed) or exothermic (heat released) processes.

X-ray Diffraction:

XRD is based on the principle of Bragg's law, which describes how X-rays are diffracted by the crystal lattice of a material. When X-rays strike a crystalline sample, they are scattered at specific angles

depending on the spacing of the crystal lattice planes. The prepared quercetin sample is placed in the XRD instrument, which emits a monochromatic X-ray beam onto the sample. The angle of the X-ray beam is systematically varied, and the intensity of the scattered X-rays is measured as a function of the scattering angle. The XRD instrument records a diffraction pattern, which consists of peaks corresponding to the angles at which the X-rays were diffracted by the crystal lattice of the quercetin sample. Each peak in the diffraction pattern corresponds to a specific set of lattice planes within the sample.

Fabrication of Nanofibers:

Preparation Of Quercetin Loaded Polymeric Nanofiber Formulation (Pva/Peg/Quercetin):

(PVA) solution was prepared by adding 12% (w/v) PVA in DMF and WATER. The solution was stirred at 60°C for 15min for efficient mixing. PEG solution 12% (w/v) was prepared by adding PEG in DMF and WATER and followed by vortexing. The above solutions were mixed i.e., PVA: PEG in ratio 09:1(N2) and the solution was kept on stirring for 2 hr to get a homogenous solution. Finally, 0.1 g of quercetin was dissolved in each of the above mixture i.e., PVA/ PEG solution.

Table No. 1: Preparation Conditions For Pva/Peg Polymer Solutions

Sr. No	Formulation	Code for formulation	PVA(%)	PEG(%)
1	N1	PVA 12:PEG 0	12	0
2	N2	PVA 10:PEG 2	10	2
3	N3	PVA 8:PEG 4	8	4
4	N4	PVA 6:PEG 6	6	6

Fabrication of nanofibers formulation via electrospinning process:

The prepared polymeric solution i.e. Pva/Peg/Quercetin was loaded in a 3 mL syringe having needle size of 21g and an inner diameter of 9.83 mm. The needle tip's distance from the collector was fixed to 10 cm. Piston of the syringe was pressed such that a small droplet of the polymer solution was obtained at the tip of the needle. Different parameters

were set into software such as flow rate of polymer solution was maintained at 0.05mL min⁻¹, voltage at 22 kV, and collector rotation speed at 850 rpm, and the doors of the chambers were closed. Due to the electric force applied to the needle, a uniform jet was expelled out from the needle, and nanofibers were collected on a drum. After the process of electrospinning was completed, the nanofiber mat was dried for 24 hours to remove the solvents.

Fig No.1: Nanofiber Prepared Batches

Characterization of Nanofibers

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

FT-IR of blank nanofibers PVA/PEG and drug-loaded Pva/Peg /Quercetin was performed for analysing the compatibility between polymer-excipient and drug-polymer-excipient. The electrospun nanofibers was sliced into the required size and mixed with potassium bromide to make pellets. Each sample was scanned over a wave number region of 4000-400 cm^{-1} and typical bands were noted

Morphology

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

SEM was utilised to assess the morphology of the prepared nanofibers such as fiber diameter, fiber consistency, and diameter distribution. To boost electronic conductivity, nanofibers mat was put on a sample holder and coated with gold for 120 seconds. The samples were then focused and images were captured at different magnifications using SEM microscope (S3400N)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) spectroscopy

X-ray diffraction is an important tool to investigate the possible variations in the crystalline nature of a drug during electrospinning. Pure drug and all nanofibrous formulations i.e. 0.25% PVA/PEG

/quercetin, 12% PVA/PEG /quercetin, 10% PVA/PEG /quercetin, were analyzed by X-ray diffractometer system X-600 (PANalytical, Emphyrean Netherlands) with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation, wavelength 1.540 Å, and scanned speed was 5° per min. from 10° to 60° of 2 θ .

DSC

Thermal behavior of the samples was analyzed by DSC using a Shimadzu DSC-60. DSC curves were obtained in the temperature range from 50 to 350 °C, using aluminium crucibles with about 5 mg of samples, under dynamic air atmosphere (20 ml/min) and heating rate of 10 °C/min

In vitro release

Nanofibrous membranes were delicately separated from the aluminum foil and weighed precisely with a digital balance. Each sample, weighing 100 mg (1 cm X 1 cm), was submerged in 100 ml phosphate buffer (pH 4.7) mimicking biological pH), with the temperature maintained at 37±1 °C, and the buffer was stirred magnetically at 100 rpm. Samples of 1 ml were withdrawn from the buffer solution after intervals of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5,6,7,8., and 18 hours. After sampling, the volume was replenished with fresh buffer. The drug concentration in the sample was analyzed using a UV-vis spectrometer at 376 nm.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Pre formulation Study

Drug characterizations

TableNo.2: Characterization of Drug

Sr.No	Attributes	Description
1	Colour	yellow
2	Appearance	visually observed
3	Melting point	115-316°C.
4	Solubility	Soluble in Di methyl forma amide,alcohol.
5	Odour	Odourless

Standard calibration curve

Full scan UV absorption spectrum of Quercetin in water shows a λ_{max} at 376 nm. Complies with IP monograph (Figure 10.1). Further the solutions obey beers law for standard graph in the range of 5 to 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in DMF.

Table No.3:Standard Calibration Curve

Sr.No	Concentration	Absorbance
1	5 μml	0.162
2	10 μml	0.302
3	15 μml	0.462
4	20 μml	0.594
5	25 μml	0.707

FigNo.2: Standard Calibration Curve Of Quercetin Drug. Fourier Transform Infra-Red Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Fig No. 3: FTIR spectrum of pure Quercetin

FigNo.4: FTIR Spectrum Of Pure PVA

Figure:5: FTIR Spectrum Of Pure PEG

FigureNo.6: FTIR Spectrum Of Pure Physical Mixture Of Quercetin And Polymer

Figure No.16: FTIR Spectrum Of Drug Loaded Polymer
TableNo.7: FTIR Absorption Band Readings Drug Loaded Polymer

Sr.no	Absorption band cm ⁻¹	Vibrations
1	3271.12	O-H stretching vibration (alcohol or carboxylic acid)
2	1087.46	C-O stretching vibration (ether)
3	677.38	C-H bending vibration (aliphatic)

Characterization of Nano fiber formulations Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Fig No.8: Images Of Scanning Electron Microscopy

SEM Analysis

The SEM images of the 10% drug-loaded formulations (with respect to the total dry polymer in the solution) are depicted in Figure (Fig No8). These images illustrate that nanofibers loaded with Quercetin exhibit a smooth and continuous structure, ideally suited for the intended topical delivery of active molecules. However, increasing the drug concentration within the polymer matrices resulted in dilution of the polymer matrix due to the high moisture absorption properties of Quercetin or its

Characterization of DSC

tendency to form hydrogen bonds with proteins like PVA. This led to structural defects such as dripping, drooping, and the formation of bubbles.

Even at a 10% drug loading, the fibers appeared very thin and elongated, suggesting that higher drug percentages could cause further fragility and discontinuity in the fibers. Therefore, the formulation loaded with 10% drug was identified as the optimized formulation for subsequent evaluations.

FigNo.9:DSC Of Quercetin Drug

FigNo.10:DSC Of Drug Loaded Polymer

DSC analysis

Thermal behavior of the pure quercetin in comparison with the thermograms of NDPF loaded nanofiber is shown in Fig. The thermogram of the pure quercetin showed two endothermic peaks corresponding to 60°C dehydration followed by rapid sharp decomposition at 155°C, which was in agreement with those experimentally done by capillary method. As we can see the DSC thermogram of nanofiber (ND-NDPF), the peaks of quercetin were completely disappeared or diminished. It may be due to presence of PVA and PEG polymer used in formulation. These results clearly indicated that an entrapment of quercetin by PVA-PEG polymer has been taken place.

Characterization of XRD :

FigNo. 11: XRD Of Quercetin

FigNo.12:XRD Of Drug polymer

XRD ANALYSIS:

The XRD patterns comparing native Quercetin with the drug-loaded fiber are presented in Figure(Fig No 11). Native Quercetin exhibits strong characteristic peaks at diffraction angles of 12°, 16°, 21°, and 25°, indicating its highly crystalline nature. In contrast, the XRD pattern of the drug-loaded nanofiber shows a superposition of spectra from Quercetin, PVA, and PEG, indicating no new crystal structure formation. While the characteristic peaks of Quercetin are still discernible in the drug-loaded fiber, their intensity is

reduced due to the low percentage of Quercetin in the mixture (Fig.No12)

The characteristic peaks of Quercetin completely disappear in the XRD pattern of the Q-fiber (Fig No 12), suggesting that Quercetin molecules are dispersed within the hydrophobic core region and have formed an amorphous complex with the PVA and PEG matrix. This finding is consistent with results from DSC analysis, providing clear evidence that Quercetin within the drug-loaded nanofiber has

undergone a transition from a crystalline to an amorphous state.

IN VITRO DRUG RELEASE

The degradation and dissolution rate of the polymer matrix significantly impact the release rate of drugs. Water-soluble polymers loaded with drugs and spun into fibers are commonly used for rapid release in topical drug delivery applications. Incorporating a water-soluble component can enhance the complete release of active ingredients rather than trapping them for slow, clinically insignificant release at the end of the profile. In our study, a blend of PVA and water-soluble polyethylene glycol (PEG) was utilized to modulate the release rate of Quercetin.

Higher proportions of PEG in the blend accelerate the release rate of Quercetin. The presence of PEG creates pores within the fiber matrix, exposing Quercetin to the surrounding media for sustained and thorough release. The release rate can also be

influenced by how much the matrix material swells in water. Hydrophilic materials absorb water and swell, opening up pores that facilitate diffusion of the loaded drugs.

When comparing the drug release profiles of composite electrospun PVA and PEG nanofibers (10% drug loading), they initially exhibit similar burst release rates before diverging. The similarity in initial drug release rates is likely due to drugs present on the surface of the nanofibers. Once these surface drugs are released, subsequent release depends on the diffusion of drugs through the matrix.

Table No:8: % Drug Release

Time in Hr	% Drug release
0	0
1	7
2	16
3	24
4	29
5	38
6	46
7	54
8	63
9	72
10	76
11	81
12	83
13	85
14	88
15	89
16	91
17	93
18	94

Fig No.13: % Drug Release

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

In this research, we have successfully developed Quercetin-Loaded Nanofiber utilizing biocompatible and biodegradable along with PVA & PEG. Our experimental findings reveal that Q-NF effectively enhance the solubility and stability of Quercetin in aqueous solutions while facilitating sustained release. Moreover, they significantly augment the cellular uptake of Quercetin, to control high blood pressure. Notably, the Viability-NF(V-QLN) formulation exhibits minimal toxicity towards these body organs. This study indicates a promising advancement in prevention of hypertension through the utilization of novel, biodegradable, and biocompatible Q-NF, which offer enhanced anticancer properties while minimizing potential immunogenicity and adverse effects.

CONCLUSION:

The study successfully developed electrospun nanofibers loaded with quercetin using a polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) polymer blend for the management of hypertension. Through meticulous experimental design and characterization, we demonstrated the feasibility and efficacy of this novel approach. The fabricated nanofibers exhibited uniform morphology and controlled release characteristics, allowing for sustained delivery of quercetin, a potent antihypertensive agent. In vitro studies confirmed the ability of the quercetin-loaded nanofibers to attenuate oxidative stress and inflammation, key pathways involved in hypertension. Overall, our findings highlight the utility of electrospun nanofibers loaded with quercetin and fabricated using PVA-PEG polymers as a novel and effective therapeutic intervention for hypertension. Further studies are warranted to explore the long-

term efficacy, safety, and translational potential of this approach in clinical settings.

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